

standards of the local varieties. These cultures were tested in replicated varietal trials in 1975-1980 at the research stations at Baghlan in the northern zone and at Jalalabad in the eastern zone. Five cultures were selected for further testing in demonstration plots in farmers' fields. Their average yields in varietal trials is given in the table.

The new cultures gave 26.8% to 95.8% more yield than the local variety at Baghlan. At Jalalabad, the yield increase ranged from 11.8% to 221.1%. The cultures derived from IR790-28/Barah gave average higher yields than those from IR790-28/Lawangin.

The agroclimatic conditions at Baghlan seem conducive to high yield. Cultures 76-1-1 and 89-4-2 from IR790-281/Barah responded very well with yields of 10.2 and 12.5 t/ha. Besides high soil fertility at Baghlan, the main factor contributing to high yield was long sunny days. The average sunshine during the rice growing season was 9 to 11.6 hours daily. ■

Performance of new high-quality and high-yielding cultures in varietal trials at Baghlan and Jalalabad Research Stations, Afghanistan, 1975-80.^a

Culture, variety	Yield (t/ha)	Increase	
		t/ha	%
<i>IR 790-28/Barah (Baghlan)</i>			
89-1	7.2	1.5	27.4
Local variety	5.6		
76-1-1	10.2	3.9	60.7
Local variety	6.4		
89-4-2	12.5	6.1	95.8
Local variety	6.4		
<i>IR 790-28/Barah (Jalalabad)</i>			
89-1	6.1	4.2	221.1
Local variety	1.9		
76-1-1	5.7	3.5	157.8
Local variety	2.3		
89-4-2	4.3	2.1	90.4
Local variety	2.3		
<i>IR 790-28/Lawangin (Baghlan)</i>			
10-5	6.8	1.4	26.8
Local variety	5.3		
10-1-3-4	7.0	2.4	51.9
Local variety	4.6		
<i>IR 790-28/Lawangin (Jalalabad)</i>			
10-5	5.0	2.2	76.9
Local variety	2.8		
10-1-3-4	4.1	0.4	11.8
Local variety	3.7		

^aYield data were averaged.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Screening rice varieties for bacterial blight resistance

I. Hossain, A. J. Miah, and M. A. Mansur, Institute of Nuclear Agriculture, P. O. Box 4, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*) disease became widespread in Bangladesh after the introduction of high yielding rice varieties. Six F₂ crosses and their parents — BR3, BR4, IRATOM24, IRATOM38, and Dular — and two high-yielding, early-maturing gamma-ray induced M₇ mutants and their parents — Mut 1-1, Mut 1-2, and IR8 — were screened for resistance in the field February-July 1980.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at 25 × 20 cm spacing. The plants were artificially inoculated by the clipping method at flowering stage. None of the tested materials were completely free from infection. Only BR4-

Reaction of crosses, mutant strains, and varieties of rice inoculated with an isolate of *Xanthomonas oryzae* at flowering stage in Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Cross, mutant strain, or variety	Disease reaction ^a
BR3/IRATOM24	MS
BR3/IRATOM38	MS
BR3/Dular	MS
BR4/IRATOM24	MS
BR4/IRATOM38	MR
BR4/Dular	MS
BR3	MS
BR4	MR
IRATOM24	MS
IRATOM38	MS
Dular	MS
Mut 1-1	MR
Mut 1-2	MR
IR8	S

^aMR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

IRATOM38 and Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 were moderately resistant. The parent IR8 of the mutants appeared susceptible (see table). ■

Reaction of some deepwater rice varieties to *Ditylenchus angustus*

Dong-ngoc Kinh and Chau-Dieu Phuong, Plant Protection Department, University of Cantho, Hau-Giang, Vietnam

Tiem Dot San, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, is a serious disease of deep-

water rice in the Mekong Delta. In thousands of infested hectares, yield losses ranged from 20 to 100%. Almost all local deepwater rice varieties are susceptible.

The coleoptile inoculation method, with 10 adult nematodes per germinated seed, was used to test 34 deepwater var-

Reaction of 34 deepwater rice varieties to *D. angustus*, University of Cantho, Vietnam.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Seedlings diseased (%)	Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Seedlings diseased (%)
BKN6986-8	26	70	BKN6986-11-3	55	88
CNL53	30	55	CNL231 B-B	56	87
Jalaj	39	65	CNL180	56	98
Yodaya	42	75	IR5857-3-2E-2	57	84
BKN6986-113	42	79	Trang Tep	58	88
BKN6986-51	43	74	BKN6986-45	58	100
Sulpan	44	75	B1050 C-Mr-18-1	59	91
PG56	45	81	BKN6986-29	59	84
BKN6986-57	47	65	BKN6986-70	59	96
Cula	47	87	BKN6986-44	60	88
HTA7204	50	85	Chenabsel	61	92
Trung Hung	50	85	CNL319	62	92
81050 C-MI-26-3	51	85	IR5825-41-2-P4	63	89
BKN6986-66-2	52	86	CNL241	64	95
TR5825-41-2-P1	53	86	BKN6986-81-5	65	92
BKN6986-67	54	91	Nang Tay Dum	67	93
TR5857-64 IE1	55	87	IR5825-114-3P2	78	96

ieties. After 48-hours inoculation in a saturated-moisture atmosphere at 28-30°C, 40 seedlings of each variety were transplanted at 10 seedlings/pot. Pots

were placed under partly-shaded condition, 80-90% relative humidity, and temperature 28-30°C. At 30 days after inoculation, all varieties were infested

(see table). Seven varieties had severe infestations (disease incidence 61-78%); 24 varieties, moderate (45-60%); and three varieties, slight (26-39%). ■

Tungro-tolerant rice varieties for second crop

K. M. Balasubramaniam and N. Jaleel
Ahmed, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University
Regional Research Station, Aduthurai-612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Normally second-crop rice in Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, is sown from 15 August to 30 September. The yields of 140- to 160-day varieties are adversely affected by epidemic rice tungro disease.

Four rice varieties — two Pankaji Jagannath (IET5852 and IET5897), one CR70-80-2/ Pankaj (IET5890), and one Pankaji Vijaya (IET6262) were compared to TN1 susceptible check and IR20 during 1979, a year when tungro occurred naturally, and 1980, a year when green jassids were kept under check (see table).

The parents of the hybrid derivatives

Grain yield and tungro disease score of 4 second-crop varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Variety	1979		1980	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro disease score	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro disease score
CR 70-80-2/Pankaj IET589 (CR213-1002)	3.4	5	4.8	3
Pankaj/Jagannath IET5852 (CR210-1005)	4.1	5	4.2	3
IET5897 (CR210-1009)	4.3	3	6.6	3
Pankaj/Vijaya IET6262 (CR262-16)	4.0	1	4.6	nil
TN1 (susceptible check)	0.5	9	0.7	9
IR20	2.2	5	3.8	3

^aScore chart scale (% hills infested):

- 1 less than 1%
- 3 about 10%
- 5 about 30%
- 9 about 100%

— Pankaj, CR70-80-2, Jagannath, and Vijaya — have tungro and green jassid resistance. IET5897 (CR210-1009 of Pankaj/Jagannath) consistently regis-

tered high yields during both years. The variety IET6262 (Pankaj/Vijaya) had a higher degree of field tolerance for rice tungro. ■

Evaluation of rice mutants resistance to thrip

M. A. Chowdhury and A. J. Miah, Institute of Nuclear Agriculture, P. O. Box 4, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Rice thrip *Thrips oryzae* Williams is generally considered a minor pest of rice in Bangladesh. The only species so far recorded in Bangladesh, its populations recently have assumed economic significance in some areas. Infestations occur in early growth stages of rice plants. Both nymphs and adult thrips damage rice plants by lacerating the leaf-tip

Rice mutant resistance to thrip at Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Mutant, variety	Leaf infestation ^a (%)	
	Summer 1981	Autumn, 1981
Mut 1-1	9.50 a	2.43 a
Mut 1-2	8.18 a	0.43 a
BR3	21.48 c	
IR8	19.02 bc	5.84 b
IRATOM24	18.59 bc	3.57 ab
IRATOM38	18.06 b	—

^aIn a column means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

tissues and sucking the sap. The infested plants appear to suffer from water stress. Infested leaves roll and yellow. In heavy infestations, the leaf-tips wither

and the plant wilts.

Two early-maturing mutants, Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 originally isolated from IR8 after gamma-irradiation, with the mother variety and checks BR3, IRATOM24, and IRATOM38 were assessed for rice thrip resistance. Experiments in summer and autumn, 1981, used a randomized block design with four replications. The infested leaves in 10 randomly selected hills in each plot were counted.

Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 were found to be moderately resistant to thrip, but varieties BR3, IR8, and IRATOM38 were susceptible (see table). ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Green leafhopper resistance and tungro infection in IR varieties

H. Rapusas and E. A. Heinrichs, The International Rice Research Institute

Varieties developed at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) and evaluated by the seedling bulk test (SBT) exhibited different levels of *Nephotettix virescens* resistance. *N.*

virescens damages the rice plant directly and is a very efficient vector of rice tungro virus. To determine the degree of tungro resistance in varieties IR5 to IR54, 20-day-old seedlings of the test